

Grounding Perspectivalism: Metaphysical Explanation in the Eye of the Beholder

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Abstract. Theorists of grounding believe that this notion has an intimate connection with metaphysical explanation. However, they struggle to harmonize the objective mind-independent features of grounding and the context-sensitive aspects of metaphysical explanation. As a reconciliatory approach, I offer a framework of metaphysical explanation that draws from perspectival realist views in the philosophy of science. According to the proposed view, our understanding of grounding claims is inescapably situated in agent-dependent perspectives that aim to aptly latch onto a grounding structure out there. To defend its merits, I discuss how this grounding perspectivalism offers an insightful analysis of disagreements concerning the priority and asymmetry of what grounds what. Exploring some of the deeper implications of the proposed framework, I conclude by stirring controversy: contrary to a popular view, grounding perspectivalism implies that metaphysical explanation should not be regarded as a guide to grounding.

Resumen. Los teóricos de la fundamentación creen que esta noción tiene una conexión íntima con la explicación metafísica. Sin embargo, les cuesta armonizar las características objetivas e independientes de la mente del fundamento y los aspectos sensibles al contexto de la explicación metafísica. Como enfoque conciliador, ofrezco un marco de explicación metafísica que se nutre de puntos de vista realistas perspectivistas en la filosofía de la ciencia. Según la perspectiva propuesta, nuestra comprensión de las afirmaciones del

fundamento se sitúa ineludiblemente en perspectivas dependientes del agente que apuntan a aferrarse adecuadamente a una estructura de fundamento existente. Para defender sus méritos, analizo cómo este perspectivismo sobre la fundamentación ofrece un análisis perspicaz de los desacuerdos sobre la prioridad y la asimetría de qué fundamenta qué. Al explorar algunas de las implicaciones más profundas del marco propuesto, concluyo provocando controversia: contrariamente a una visión popular, el perspectivismo sobre la fundamentación implica que la explicación metafísica no debe considerarse una guía para el fundamento.

1. Introduction

Among metaphysicians, there is widespread consensus about an intimate link between grounding and metaphysical explanation. But disagreement about the strength of the connection persists. We can identify two parties in the literature. Unionists believe that whenever some facts ground others, the former metaphysically explain the latter. Separatists maintain that the grounds (the facts about what does the grounding) back a metaphysical explanation of the grounded (the facts about what is grounded). However, both positions struggle to harmonize the objective features of grounding, which is standardly taken to be an objective mind-independent relation, and the subjective context-sensitive character of metaphysical explanation.¹

Both unionism and separatism face difficult challenges (cf. Maurin 2019). Unionism implies that either grounding is not objective or that metaphysical explanation is not subjective. Each disjunct clashes with the orthodox view that grounding is objective and metaphysical explanation is subjective. Since it does not force us to choose between these options, separatism is *prima facie* preferable to unionism. However, the tenability of

¹ I shall assume that grounding is a relation among facts having worldly items as constituents. The arguments discussed in this paper can be suitably generalized to other conceptions. When useful, I write [p] for *the fact that p*.

this position hangs on an explication of the backing relation. As it happens, there are competing accounts and no clear winner (e.g., Sjölin Wirling 2020; Stamatiadis-Bréhier 2021; Taylor 2022). The challenge of articulating the backing relation is an instance of a more general hurdle, which I call the *latching problem*: that of explaining how our subjective metaphysical explanations latch onto an objective grounding structure.

A solution to the latching problem is just one step toward a successful separatist account, however. We must elucidate how the context-sensitive features of metaphysical explanation and the objective aspects of grounding mesh together. To advance the debate toward this goal, I set out to articulate and defend a general framework that draws from perspectival realism in the philosophy of science. I shall call this approach “grounding perspectivalism”. In slogan form, this view holds that metaphysical explanation is a perspectival affair aimed at understanding a non-perspectival grounding structure. This paper seeks to defend this idea.

I proceed like this. In the next section, I explain what perspectivalism about grounding is by comparing it with scientific perspectivalism. In section 3, I introduce and characterize the notion of a metaphysical perspective, identifying some key roles it plays in our theorizing about grounding. In section 4, I put the resulting framework to work. Unlike its scientific counterpart, I do not defend the adoption of grounding perspectivalism by employing sociological or historical considerations about our metaphysical practice. Instead, I argue that grounding perspectivalism yields an illuminating analysis of disagreements about what grounds what. To make things more concrete, I discuss two cases: one concerns the dispute about the priority of some grounds over others, and the other concerns the possibility of symmetric grounding. In section 5, I canvass two significant implications of grounding perspectivalism, particularly concerning the latching problem. My conclusion, however, will be polemical: if grounding perspectivalism

carries the day, then, contrary to a popular view, metaphysical explanation should not be a guide to grounding.

2. Perspectivalism about grounding

In the philosophy of science, perspectivalism claims to be a middle-ground position between scientific realism and anti-realism (for an overview, see Massimi and McCoy 2021 and Massimi forthcoming). This view rejects the idea that agents like us can acquire knowledge of objective scientific truths or facts from a God's eye viewpoint. Our knowledge of the natural world is situated in, and thusly influenced by, a specific vantage point or perspective. We are situated agents. Scientific knowledge, including scientific theories and representations, modelling practices, data analysis and collection, is situated in two ways. It is historically situated because it is the product of specific historical periods. And it is culturally situated because scientific knowledge is the product of a prevailing cultural tradition.

According to the scientific perspectivalist I have in mind, scientific claims are neither true nor false *tout court* (my primary sources are Griere 1985, 2006, Massimi 2018b, Teller 2018). Rather, scientific truth is perspectival; it is truth relative to a perspective. For example, the proposition <water has the property of viscosity> gets different truth-values depending on whether it is made within the perspective of hydrodynamics or statistical mechanics. However, the scientific perspectivalist does not deny that water has some perspective-independent properties. Unsurprisingly, the difficult task is to explicate the relationship between situated agents and perspective-independent scientific states of affairs. This problem is the analogous latching problem for scientific perspectivalism. Here I do not wish to explore solutions to this issue (but see Massimi 2018a for some options). Instead, I outline scientific perspectivalism to provide the reader with a reference template for

understanding its metaphysical counterpart, namely grounding perspectivalism.

Scientific perspectivalism is typically motivated by reflections on the history of science and scientific practice. Echoing Kuhn, Massimi expresses the core idea of this view by claiming that scientific knowledge is ‘idiosyncratic to any given scientific community at any given historical time’ (2018a, p. 166). The theoretical and technological choices we invoke in interpreting the available data are bound to specific historical and cultural contexts. Someone could gather similar considerations from the history of metaphysics and metaphysical practice to defend the idea that our theorizing about grounding is situated in a somewhat similar fashion. On some interpretations, we can trace debates about what grounds what, in the West, to Plato’s Euthyphro dilemma (Schaffer 2009, p. 375; Schnieder and Correia 2012, 3–4) or even earlier than that (cf. Corkum 2020). If these accounts are correct, we would have a sizeable historical sample. However, I will not offer a socio-historical defence of grounding perspectivalism. My argument will be different: we ought to endorse grounding perspectivalism because it is a promising framework for articulating separatism about grounding and yields an insightful interpretation of metaphysical disagreements.

I believe that a socio-historical approach to grounding perspectivalism is plausible but not easy to pull off. Some metaphysical theories fall outside the jurisdiction of empirical evidence.² It is, therefore, harder to tell when such views are abandoned or unsuccessful. Complementarily, it is difficult to verify when better theories supersede older ones. Popularity is not a reliable guide for assessing metaphysical theories.

Having sketched an outline of scientific perspectivalism, I now turn to characterize the main tenets of grounding perspectivalism. To do so, I draw

² For example, think of the discussion about the grounds of negative facts. Scientific evidence does not help us adjudicating which theory we ought to endorse. For discussion of some approaches, see De Rizzo 2020; Amijee 2021.

on Massimi's (2018b) description of the components of its scientific analogue. However, for space reasons, I shall not discuss a comparison between my approach and Massimi's.

I suggest that any version of grounding perspectivalism is committed to the following three claims or some variants thereof.

Metaphysical claim: There are perspective-independent grounding facts. (i.e., facts of the form $[[p] \text{ grounds } [q]]$)

Semantic claim: The truth-value of propositions of the form $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is perspective-dependent.³

Epistemic claim: The explanatoriness of propositions of the form $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is perspective-dependent.

In addition, I submit an extra normative claim expressing the realist commitment of the perspectivalist framework. This claim captures the idea that our grounding theories ought to get grounding facts right.

Normative claim: Perspective-dependent metaphysical explanations should aim at latching onto a perspective-independent grounding structure.

The above tenets constitute the core of grounding perspectivalism. Other principles are negotiable. However, to assess this framework, we must give an account of what a perspective is and explain the idea of perspective-dependence. The next section will do just that.

³ To ease the discussion, I shall often refer to propositions like $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ as grounding claims.

3. The Functional Conception of Perspectives

Metaphorically speaking, we can say that perspectives are like vantage points or frames to make sense of the world. Since my focus is on grounding, the notion of a perspective I will articulate is tailored to the metaphysical debate (and when I use ‘perspective’, I mean ‘metaphysical perspective’). I shall remain neutral on whether the proposed conception extends to scientific perspectives.

I will often talk of agents being situated in a perspective, or situated agents. But I won’t say how to understand this claim more precisely. The arguments in this paper do not force us to fix on a specific conception. If needed, we can think of the being-situated-in relation as kindred to the set-membership relation. And we can regard a perspective as a set having agents and the roles I identify below as members.

I am sceptical about the prospects of an informative reductive analysis of what a perspective is. Instead, I assume that we have a pre-theoretical conception and characterize a perspective in functional terms: namely, by identifying the main roles it plays in our theorizing. Then, I suggest that we can group the roles of a perspective into dimensions. However, a complete metaphysics of perspectives will remain beyond the scope of this paper. Talk of roles and dimensions should be regarded as capturing and explicating various ways a perspective influences situated agents in assessing and producing grounding claims. It should not be interpreted as carrying heavyweight metaphysical implications. A fair assessment of the proposal requires us to bear in mind four points.

First, I will not attempt to argue that dimensions (and thus roles) can be accurately individuated in terms of necessary and sufficient conditions.

Second, I will not attempt to identify well-defined individuation and identity criteria for perspectives.

Third, we should acknowledge that perspectives can be nested. One could be a proper part of another. However, I suggest that we set aside this extra complication for now.

Lastly, we should recognize that the roles that perspectives play are intimately intertwined. They are mutually supporting each other. Related to this clarification, we should consider perspectives as dynamic “things” rather than static.

I single out three core dimensions of a perspective, grouping the roles it plays: one is semantic, another is explanatory, and a further other is normative. Below, I explain each of these in turn. Before that, I flag an important difference with scientific perspectives. As I understand it, scientific perspectivalism is primarily concerned with practices related to scientific *knowledge*. By contrast, my favourite conception of grounding perspectivalism focuses on how we *understand* metaphysical claims. Knowledge and understanding are close-knit notions. Depending on your favourite view, one could entail the other (e.g., Grimm 2006). However, some epistemologists believe that knowing and understanding come apart (e.g., deRegt 2015, 2016; Dellsén 2017; for more on this, Elgin 2007, Kvanvig 2003, Pritchard 2010). Good news if the separation happens. The proposed grounding perspectivalism would be more appealing to those who think that metaphysics is primarily in the business of accruing understanding rather than knowledge.

3.1 The Semantic Dimension

The semantic dimension, as I call it, captures the various ways a perspective influences how we assess the truth of propositions of the form $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$. By drawing on Massimi (2018a), I propose three main semantic roles grouped under this dimension.

3.1.1 *The Truthmaking role*

A perspective plays a truthmaking role in the sense that it determines the truthmakers of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ -type of propositions. To put it differently, the truthmakers of grounding claims are perspective-dependent. Which portions of reality make our grounding claims true depends on the perspective of situated agents. For example, on a certain perspective, the truthmakers of $\langle [\text{the ball is scarlet}] \text{ grounds } [\text{the ball is red}] \rangle$ might comprise these facts plus the grounding law that facts about determinates ground fact about determinable (cf. Schaffer 2017; Rosen 2017). By contrast, a perspective that dispenses with grounding laws would specify that the truthmakers of $\langle [\text{the ball is scarlet}] \text{ grounds } [\text{the ball is red}] \rangle$ are just these facts.

3.1.2 *Semantic role*

A perspective determines the truth-value of propositions about what grounds what. On the grounding perspectivalist account, the truth of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is perspective-dependent iff for some perspectives P and P^* , $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is true in P , and it is false in P^* . For example, if $\langle [\text{the ball is scarlet}] \text{ grounds } [\text{the ball is red}] \rangle$ is perspective-dependent, then there are some perspectives in which this proposition is true and some others in which it is false.⁴

3.1.3 *Contextual Role*

A perspective determines the truth-conditions of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ -type of propositions, namely the circumstances defining how things should be for them to be true. The truth-conditions, C , of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ are perspective-dependent iff for some perspectives P and P^* , $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$

⁴ For example, $\langle [\text{the ball is scarlet}] \text{ grounds } [\text{the ball is red}] \rangle$ is false relative to perspectives on which determinables ground determinates; cf. Wilson 2012.

is true in P when C is satisfied, and $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is not true in P* when C is satisfied.

Putting things together, we could say that the semantic dimension of a perspective dictates what Massimi calls the ‘context of assessment’ (2018a, 13) for grounding claims. It gives us the conditions and rules under which $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is truth-evaluable relative to a specific perspective.

Before turning to the next dimension, it is worth noting that this characterization is silent on whether some grounding claims are true across perspectives. Nor does it imply that grounding claims are not assessable from the viewpoint of other perspectives. I shall expand on these remarks in discussing the normative dimension of perspectives and then again in section 5.

3.2 The Explanatory Dimension

The explanatory dimension captures how a perspective influences our judgements about the explanatoriness of grounding relationships. On grounding perspectivalism, whether $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is explanatory is a perspective-dependent affair. It is therefore possible that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is explanatory in perspective P but not in P*. If this is the case, then $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is explanatorily perspective-dependent. The claim that the explanatoriness of grounding claims is perspectival is the core of the proposed framework. It accommodates the separatist insight that grounding explanation is a highly context-sensitive phenomenon.

I identify two reciprocally supporting roles grouped under the explanatory dimension of perspectives: one is an understanding-enhancing role, and the other is legislative.

3.2.1 Understanding-enhancing role

This role captures the idea that whether an agent judges $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ as explanatory is determined by whether such a claim is deemed as understanding-enhancing. In turn, according to the grounding perspectivist, whether $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is understanding-enhancing is influenced by the perspective of the situated agent. Schematically, we could formulate these remarks as follows.⁵

Understanding-Explanation Link: If $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is understanding-enhancing for some agent situated in P, then $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is explanatory for that agent in P.

Perspectival Explanatoriness: $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is explanatorily perspectival iff for some perspectives P and P* and some agents s and s*, $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is understanding-enhancing for s in P, and it is not for s* in P*.

Before I suggest how to fill in the schemata with some examples, I wish to stress that grounding perspectivalism is suitable for a variety of conceptions of understanding, explanation, and the link between them. However, by endorsing the above *Link* principle, I side with those who embrace the idea that explanation and understanding are closely related (Achinstein 1983, Salmon 1998, Friedman 1974, Woodward 2003, Kitcher 1981). Here, I have a counterfactual conception of understanding in mind.⁶

⁵ We can precisify the schemata by temporally indexing them. I want to keep things simple. So, I shall omit temporal variables in the discussion.

⁶ Saatsi (2021) defends an explanatory approach to scientific perspectivalism. An important difference with grounding perspectivalism is that understanding is subjective on this view. By contrast, Saatsi defends an objective form of understanding, which requires an agent to correctly map counterfactual to the world. This is not required by grounding perspectivalism. The very idea of correctly mapping to the world seems to imply that an agent can go beyond their perspective. The grounding perspectivist denies this possibility.

On my preferred view, understanding implies the possession of some representational abilities or dispositions to answer specific what-if-things-had-been-different questions (see Grimm 2006, 2014 for a more sophisticated discussion). For example, if Ines understands that \langle [the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red] \rangle , they should be able to form and evaluate certain counterfactuals about what would happen to the grounded fact if [the ball is scarlet] had been different. This proposal fits nicely with the idea that the counterfactuals relevant for understanding are interventionist (cf. Woodward 2003): they are counterfactuals that involve an agent manipulating the grounds and assessing what happens to the grounded. (see Schaffer 2016 and Wilson 2018 for a discussion of grounding interventionism; see Miller and Norton 2022 for a similar proposal about our understanding of everyday metaphysical dependencies.)

We should be prepared to abandon the idea that an agent's understanding demands the correct truth-evaluation of all counterfactuals of interest. The bar is too high if we expect that an ordinary agent should be able to correctly truth-evaluate counterfactuals associated with every grounding structure. Some of these may have grounds and grounded connected through an intricate web of relationships whose corresponding counterfactuals are too hard to evaluate. This claim leaves open the question of which counterfactuals are relevant in assessing an agent's understanding of a grounding claim. An unsatisfactory yet unsurprising answer is that the standards of assessment depend on the perspective of the situated agent. A perspective may specify a range of counterfactuals that should be correctly evaluated. Presumably, an agent who correctly truth-evaluates many of such counterfactual has a higher-degree of understanding than an agent who does not. Such a range could be perspective-dependent. Accordingly, there may be perspectives under which understanding is more accessible, and others where it is less so. I will return to this issue in discussing the normative dimension of perspective. For now, let us set aside these complicated epistemic matters

concerning what understanding is. Instead, let us consider an example that will illustrate the above formulations. Ines judges that the <[the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red]> is explanatory because this grounding claim is understanding-enhancing for them. Nina, who is situated in a different perspective, does not judge it as explanatory; the claim that <[the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red]>] does not produce any understanding. If so, <[the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red]> is explanatorily perspectival. On my suggested view of understanding, Ines understands that <[the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red]> because they are able to form and correctly evaluate certain counterfactuals about what would happen to [the ball is red] if [the ball is scarlet] had been different.⁷

3.2.2 Legislative Role

A perspective plays a legislative role, meaning that it partly determines what counts as explanatory, and thus understanding-enhancing, for a situated agent. This phrasing may sound odd. But it captures an ordinary and widely accepted fact: the context of an explanation influences what an agent counts as explanatory. Since I am operating with an understanding-based approach to explanation, whether an agent judges a grounding claim as explanatory is also partly determined by their cognitive abilities. This latter claim should be uncontroversial. We can employ the previous example to illustrate the legislative role. Suppose that Ines is situated in a perspective that licenses grounding explanations of determinables in terms of their determinates. Accordingly, Ines would be disposed to judge a proposition such as <[the ball is scarlet] grounds [the ball is red]> as explanatory. I say ‘disposed to judge’ because whether Ines actually does so depends on the

⁷ It is worth noting that an agent might switch judgement about the explanatoriness of a target grounding claim. Such a change might occur because the agent changes perspective. We should leave open this possibility. However, here I won’t explore how a change in perspective might happen.

specific circumstances Ines is asked to perform their judgement. A lot of things may hinder the manifestation of a situated agent's epistemic abilities. Also this point should be uncontroversial.

It seems to me that the understanding-enhancing and the legislative roles are mutually supporting. What grounding claims a situated agent considers as understanding-enhancing is influenced by what the perspective prompts or predisposes them to regard as explanatory. Complementarily, what grounding claims are judged as explanatory is influenced by what a situated agent is disposed to consider as understanding-enhancing.

3.3 The Normative Dimension

I now turn to the normative dimension of a perspective, which groups the various ways it influences an agent's evaluation and systematization of grounding claims. Under this dimension, I suggest that we can distinguish between epistemically normative roles and non-epistemic ones—though we should be liberal on whether the classification is mutually exclusive. The epistemically normative role consists of the various ways we ought to gather evidence for, produce, and assess grounding claims. The non-epistemically normative role concerns the various ways grounding claims ought to be considered against a background of commitments and values. We can think of these roles as collectively providing the normative conditions that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ -type of propositions have to satisfy to be accepted in our theory. Since these normative conditions are perspective-dependent, it is possible that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ satisfies the normative conditions of a perspective but not those of another. When this happens, $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is normatively perspectival. Before illustrating this idea, I expand on these normative roles.

3.3.1 Epistemically Normative Role

A perspective influences an agent's formation and assessment of grounding claims by providing them with some guiding epistemic norms. These include principles about what sort of evidence ought to be considered in evaluating grounding claims as well as norms about how such claims are then justified. The proposed grounding perspectivalist framework is meant to be compatible with many conceptions of evidence and justification. As such, we can use these notions as a placeholder for more specific ones.⁸ An example will illustrate the idea. An agent situated in a naturalistic perspective, such as the outlook defended by Ladyman and Ross (2007), would plausibly endorse the norm the grounding claims ought to be formulated only on the basis of scientific evidence. Another norm associated with this perspective could be that grounding claims ought to be assessed only for the philosophical benefits they bring to our scientific theories. By contrast, an agent situated in a perspective that privileges *a priori* theorizing would presumably reject both norms. For example, they could be replaced with the norm that grounding claims ought to be assessed by considering whether they limn debates of interest (cf. Dasgupta 2016).

Presumably, the epistemically normative roles also include so-called cognitive values, which are often discussed in the literature of scientific theories. Accuracy, internal consistency, simplicity, and fruitfulness are a few examples. Analogous values are plausibly encoded in the epistemically normative role of perspectives. For example, a not-so-surprising norm that seems to be shared across perspectives is that grounding claims ought to be consistent with other accepted grounding claims. Many of these norms embedding cognitive values are tacitly endorsed by the overwhelming majority of the participants in debates about grounding. Thus, this remark could be trivial.

⁸ See Miller and Norton 2022 for a discussion of the epistemic and cognitive mechanisms that may be involved in evaluating metaphysical dependencies.

3.3.2 Non-epistemically Normative Role

Under this role, I suggest that we locate the various ways a perspective determines the non-epistemic theoretical and ideological commitments for assessing grounding claims. A perspective not only influences how we assess grounding claims but also determines how these claims ought to be systematized in our theorizing—under a suite of values and background commitments. For example, a “conservative” perspective might endorse the norm that we ought to preserve only one conception of grounding. Agents situated in this perspective would not admit a variety of kinds of grounding. By contrast, a more “liberal” perspective might dispense with such a norm. Agents situated in this perspective might be happy to posit more conceptions of grounding serving an array of different theoretical purposes. (For example, see the discussion of Baron-Schmitt 2020 and Cohen 2021 on different kinds of grounding.)

It seems that perspectives also determine some noncognitive values we put on the scale in evaluating grounding claims. In the philosophy of science, there is a debate on whether noncognitive values ought to influence our scientific practice (e.g., Harding 1986; Longino 1990, Lacey 1999, Anderson 2004). Examples of noncognitive values are social, political, and moral values. For example, recent inputs from feminist metaphysics strongly suggest that our metaphysical theorizing is not exempt from considerations about gender (e.g., Passinsky 2021, Barnes 2014, 2017, Mikkola 2015, 2017). If we pay heed to this insight, situated agents might assess grounding claims with respect to such noncognitive values as well. For instance, an agent situated in a broadly feminist perspective would judge as unacceptable a grounding claim that clashes with core feminist values.

To sum up, we can say that a perspective determines the various norms, epistemic and non-epistemic, a situated agent invokes to evaluate grounding

claims. These norms specify the normative conditions that must be satisfied by a grounding claim in order to be accepted. Consider two situated agents: Nadia and Nora. Nadia is situated in a perspective encoding the norm that we ought to accept grounding claims if they have an intuitive appeal. Nora is situated in a different perspective, one which has a norm that a grounding claim must satisfy an extra condition, whatever that is, to be accepted. For Nadia, that \langle [Hypatia exists] grounds [$\{$ Hypatia} exists] \rangle is intuitively appealing and thus acceptable since it satisfies the norm. For Nora, the intuitive appeal of \langle [Hypatia exists] grounds [$\{$ Hypatia} exists] \rangle is not enough to yield acceptance. Supposing that the extra condition is not satisfied, Nora does not accept that that \langle [Hypatia exists] grounds [$\{$ Hypatia} exists] \rangle . In this sense, the proposition \langle [Hypatia exists] grounds [$\{$ Hypatia} exists] \rangle is normatively perspectival.

4. Perspectival Disagreement

So far, I have painted in broad strokes a conception of perspectives to explicate the claims of grounding perspectivalism. I identified three main entangled dimensions (semantic, explanatory, and normative) and offered examples to illustrate the general picture. Unsurprisingly, there is a lot more that could be said about perspectives. But what I presented suffices for the following task: I turn to argue that grounding perspectivalism gives us an insightful framework for analyzing disagreement about grounding claims. To make my case, I will discuss two live debates from the grounding literature: one concerns disagreement about priority, and the other concerns the possibility of mutually grounded facts.

In defending this application, I show that the grounding perspectival framework escapes an objection that is often made against perspectivalism: namely, that it dissipates genuine disagreements. To clarify this objection, I propose to consider an example from scientific perspectivalism (Massimi

2018a, 10–12; cf. Goodman 1978). Take the proposition <the Earth is orbiting the Sun>. In the Ptolemaic perspective, it is false. In the Copernican perspective, it is true. The alleged problem is that if the truth of <the Earth is orbiting the Sun> is perspective-dependent in this fashion, there is no genuine conflict about the perspective-independent truth-value of this proposition. Someone can raise a structurally analogous objection for grounding claims. For instance, <physical facts ground mental facts> is true relative to the grounding physicalist perspective (e.g., Schaffer 2009, Rosen 2010, deRosset 2013, Dasgupta 2014) but false relative to non-physicalist perspectives (see Blaesi in progress and J. M. Wilson 2018 for a discussion about grounding physicalism). It would be a troublesome consequence of the perspectivalist approach if physicalists and non-physicalists were not having a genuine disagreement about the grounds of mental facts. Fortunately, I will argue, grounding perspectivalism does not render disagreement non-genuine. Quite the contrary: as I shall explain, it gives us tools for offering a rich and layered analysis of disagreements about what grounds what in terms of differences between the perspectives of the disagreeing parties.

It seems to me that disputes about what grounds what shared four features that a good account disagreement should capture (cf. Ranalli 2020):

- (i) The disagreeing parties, when they have a genuine disagreement, do not see themselves as having merely verbal disputes.
- (ii) The disagreeing parties have reasons for holding contrasting views.
- (iii) The disagreement among parties is systematic. That is, parties that disagree on one proposition disagree on related propositions.
- (iv) The disagreement among parties is persistent.

My claim is that if we conceive of grounding disagreements from the viewpoint of the perspectivalist framework, we can tick all the boxes.

To start, the grounding perspectivalist distinguishes between perspective-dependent and perspective-independent disagreement. Schematically, we can say that a disagreement about $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is perspective-dependent iff for some perspectives P and P*, one party judges that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is true in P and $\langle \sim([p] \text{ grounds } [q]) \rangle$ is false in P, and another party judges that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is false in P* and $\langle \sim([p] \text{ grounds } [q]) \rangle$ is true in P*. In turn, perspectival disagreement can be strict and non-strict. In the previous sense, it is strict. It non-strict when for some perspectives P and P*, one party judges that $\langle ([p] \text{ grounds } [q]) \rangle$ is true in P and another party judges that $\langle [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$ is true in P*.

A perspective-independent disagreement about $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \rangle$ is when parties disagree on how things stand in the grounding structure, namely on whether $[[p] \text{ grounds } [q]]$ obtains. As for perspective-dependent disagreement, we can distinguish between strict and non-strict perspective-independent disagreement. We can de-relativize the above template, replacing truth and falsity of $\langle ([p] \text{ grounds } [q]) \rangle$ with the obtaining or non-obtaining of $[[p] \text{ grounds } [q]]$. Intuitively, perspective-independent disagreements are genuine since they concern what grounding facts obtain independently of any specific perspective.

I propose a perspectivalist interpretation of grounding disagreement. Accordingly, disagreeing parties have a genuine disagreement when they have conflicting views about the obtaining of certain perspective-independent facts about grounding. The substantivity of certain disagreements can be ensured by ascribing the *Metaphysical Claim* to the disagreeing parties (section 1). However, grounding perspectivalism warns us that whether disagreeing parties have a perspective-independent disagreement is less immediate than one might suppose. It requires us to consider the perspectives

of the disagreeing parties. This claim will become apparent in illustrating the two cases.⁹

4.1 Perspectival Priority

Grounding theorists typically agree that this concept has a tight connection with both absolute and relative fundamentality. Two entry-level principles that we can find discussed in the literature are these:

$G \rightarrow \text{MFT}$: If $[p]$ grounds $[q]$, then $[p]$ is more fundamental than $[q]$.

$\text{UG} \rightarrow \text{F}$: If nothing grounds $[p]$, then $[p]$ is fundamental.

Here I do not wish to assess the correctness of these principles (for stronger formulations and discussion, see Wilson 2014; Cameron 2015; Bennett 201; Giannotti 2021). My point of interest here is that $G \rightarrow \text{MFT}$, even when accepted among participants in the debate, is employed to defend conflicting claims.

To make things more concrete, let us discuss an unsettled debate. Consider the disagreement between an “atomist” and a priority monist à la Schaffer (2010). For the atomist, the parts ground and are thus prior to the whole (a shorthand for ‘facts about the parts ground and are therefore more fundamental than facts about the whole’). For the priority monist, it is the other way round. Such a disagreement is about what is prior to what.

My suggestion is that we can illuminate the disagreement between the atomist and the priority monist by interpreting in perspectivalist terms. By paying heed to the differences among the relevant perspectives, an insightful analysis emerges. We can account for the disagreement between the atomist

⁹ I discuss two cases of non-strict disagreement because they better serve the moral of this paper. However, the considerations I offer apply to strict disagreements about grounding claims as well.

and the priority monist in terms of differences between perspectives. We can apply a similar perspectivalist approach to other debates of interest. And if this interpretation is fruitful, we can maintain that differences in the perspectives of disagreeing parties contribute to the persistence of certain metaphysical debates about what is prior to what. To see how this proposal works, let us return to our case.

The semantic dimension of the atomist and priority monist perspectives determines the respective truth-value conditions, truthmakers, and truth-value assignments for propositions of the form $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$ and $\langle [w] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$, where this time $[p]$ is a variable for facts about the existence of some parts and $[w]$ is a variable for facts about the existence of some whole. As expected, $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$ is true in the atomist perspective. By contrast, the priority monist perspective yields that $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$ is false, whereas $\langle [w] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$ is true.¹⁰

Next, consider the explanatory dimension. On the atomist perspective, it is plausible that situated agents regard $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$ as understanding-enhancing, but this is not so for $\langle [w] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$. Presumably, it is the opposite for an agent situated in the priority monist perspective. On the perspectivalist interpretation, the atomist and the priority monist are not just disagreeing about the truth-values of certain grounding claims; they also disagree on what grounding claims count as explanatory.

Lastly, focus on the normative dimension, which determines the different ways grounding claims are assessed against a backdrop of normative conditions. Quite plausibly, the atomist and the priority monist are situated in perspectives differing in the normative conditions (section 3.3) that grounding claims about parts and wholes ought to satisfy to be accepted. For example, a priority monist like Schaffer is plausibly situated in a perspective that

¹⁰ How to fill in $[p]$ and $[w]$ is a delicate business. Such facts might have a richer structure than the main texts suggests. The example is merely illustrative.

includes a norm for the evaluation of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$ following specific interpretations of quantum theory (for what these interpretations are, see his joint work with Ismael 2020). By contrast, an atomist might be situated in a perspective that does include such norms. For such a situated atomist, in assessing whether $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [w] \rangle$, we ought not to consider the sort of interpretations from quantum theory that Ismael and Schaffer (2020) employ to bolster priority monism.

On the proposed interpretation, it becomes evident why the disagreement between the atomist and the priority atomist is supported by reasons, systematic, and persistent. The various roles of these two conflicting perspectives provide the situated agents with reasons to endorse the grounding claims they do and reject the opposite. We also get an explanation of why the disagreement between atomist and the priority monist is persistent: it is not just a disagreement concerning the truth-value of some grounding claims about parts and wholes. Rather it is more profound, involving differences about what counts as explanatory and how we ought to evaluate grounding claims of interest.

Crucially, the perspectivalist interpretation recovers the idea that the disagreement between the atomist and the priority monist is genuine. If both views encode the *Metaphysical* and the *Normative Claims* (section 1), the disagreement is about perspective-independent grounding facts.

The analysis of the disagreement between the atomist and the priority monists that emerges from the perspectivalist interpretation is suitably generalizable to other cases. A deep consequence arises: if we endorse grounding perspectivalism, what is prior to what depends, in some sense, on us. For the atomist, the parts are prior to the whole. For the priority monist, it is the other way round. We face an immediate question: Is there a perspective-independent priority direction between parts and wholes? I shall hint at how to approach this question in the last section. Before that, let us consider the second case.

4.2 Perspectival Asymmetry

The standard view is that grounding relationships are asymmetric (Schaffer 2009, Rosen 2010, Fine 2012). In recent years, however, some metaphysicians have legitimized “heretic” positions defending the possibility of non-asymmetric grounding (J. M. Wilson 2014, Thompson 2016, Bliss 2018, Giannotti 2021). Putative cases of symmetric grounding include the relationship between the two magnetic poles of a magnet, between the parameters of mass, density and volume of a homogenous fluid, and between the entangled components of an entangled state (cf. Ismael and Schaffer 2020). There is a clear-cut disagreement between the standard view and these heretic positions. In this sub-section, I argue that the grounding perspectivalist interpretation yields an insightful account of the dispute among these conflicting positions.

Let us briefly consider each dimension in turn, starting with the semantic one. The perspective of the standard view (‘the standard perspective’) and that of the heretic positions (which, for the sake of simplicity, I group under the ‘the heretic perspective’) determine different truth-value conditions and truth-value assignments for grounding claims of the form $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$. For an agent situated in the standard perspective, $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$ is always false whenever $[p] \text{ grounds } [q]$. By contrast, for the agent situated in the heretic perspective, $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$ is sometimes true.

Now let us consider the explanatory dimension. Arguably, agents situated in the standard perspective are disposed to judge $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$ as non-explanatory (i.e., it is not understanding-enhancing). By contrast, some agents situated in the heretic position could be disposed to judge symmetric grounding claims as explanatory. Such a difference about the explanatoriness of $\langle [p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p] \rangle$

is a very credible source of disagreement between the standard view and the heretic positions. However, the perspectivalist interpretation does not force us to maintain that every situated heretic accepts the explanatoriness symmetric grounding claims. The grounding perspectivalist framework can locate another source of contention between these views in some normative differences. Things here get deeply interesting for those who buy into the grounding perspectivalist story.

The normative dimension of a perspective includes the various norms and commitments that influence the ways an agent evaluates a grounding claim (section 3.2). Proponents of the standard view believe that the structural features of grounding are inherited by those of metaphysical explanation. For example, Rosen motivates the asymmetry of grounding by arguing that ‘when we cite grounds for [p], we cite facts that are strictly prior to [p] in a certain explanatory order.’ (2010, p. 116). Raven claims that ‘just as cyclical explanations are prohibited, so too are cycles of ground’ (2013, pp. 93 – 194). And Trogdon says that ‘the fact that grounding is systematically connected with explanation in this way suggests that grounding, like explanation generally speaking, is asymmetric’ (2013, p.106). The commitment expressed by such statements is out-and-out normative, the grounding perspectivalist would argue.

Giving credit to Maurin (2019), let us call *inheritance* the norm that grounding relationship ought to possess the structural features of explanation. It is very plausible that the standard perspective contains such a norm. Accordingly, we have a normative explanation of why a standard agent (i.e., an agent situated in the standard perspective) is not willing to accept symmetric grounding claims: they clash with the inheritance norm. By contrast, the heretic agent (i.e., an agent situated in the heretic perspective)

does not endorse the inheritance norm. For such an agent, the evaluation of symmetric grounding claims is free from such a constraint.¹¹

If the perspectivalist interpretation is correct, it becomes apparent why the disagreement between the standard view and the heretic positions is supported by reasons, systematic, and persistent. By giving centre stage to the normative difference between these perspectives, we can explain why these positions appear to be in a deadlock. The standard view and the heretic positions disagree due to different normative commitments about how the evaluation of grounding claims ought to be performed.

The perspectivalist interpretation can establish that the disagreement between the standard view and the heretic positions is genuine. If the disagreeing parties adopt the *Metaphysical* and *Normative Claims* of grounding perspectivalism (section 1), the debate on whether grounding is symmetric is perspective-independent. It concerns whether facts of the form $[[p] \text{ grounds } [q] \text{ and } [q] \text{ grounds } [p]]$ obtain perspective-independently.

As per the discussion about priority (section 4.1), however, we might wonder whether there are some perspective-independent facts about the asymmetry or non-asymmetry of grounding. I tackle this question in the imminent last section.

5. Speculations

In the previous sections, I outlined a grounding perspectivalist framework and argued that it offers an insightful and sophisticated analysis of disagreements about grounding claims. Many areas of this proposal need further clarification. But I believe that the account provided, albeit programmatic, is plausible and immediately compelling. I conclude by

¹¹ Some heretic perspectives may encode a version of the inheritance norm that countenance symmetric explanations (see Thompson 2018). The disagreement between perspectives would still be normative. There would be a difference with respect to the kind of norms that situated agents invoke when they evaluate the acceptance of symmetric grounding claims.

pointing out two significant implications that the proposed framework yields, thereby clearing the path to future expansions of this work. In closing, I hint at a strategy to address whether there are perspective-independent facts about grounding and its features.

5.1 Metaphysical Explanation Should Not Be a Guide to Grounding

Grounding is routinely introduced by invoking its close link with metaphysical explanation. This practice is common among unionists who believe that grounding is metaphysical explanation. But separatists often do the same. The underlying reason, I take it, is that metaphysical explanation reveals something important about the nature of grounding and its role in our theorizing. However, grounding perspectivalism prompts us to scrutinize the origin of such an idea. On the perspectivalist view, the belief that metaphysical explanation is a guide to grounding is—very plausibly—encoded in the normative dimension of a widely shared perspective among grounding theorists of various stripes. But the perspective-dependency of such a commitment should make us wary of the possibility that metaphysical explanation reliably unveils the non-perspectival explanatory nature of grounding. My claim is not that nothing good comes out of taking metaphysical explanation as a guide to grounding. Rather my claim is that this perspective-dependent commitment is a bad guide to the perspective-independent nature of grounding.

I suggest that we take seriously the idea of switching perspective. More specifically, we should entertain the thought of relaxing or rejecting the link between grounding and metaphysical explanation. The discussion of the disagreement about symmetric grounding claims suggests that if we relax the commitment to the inheritance norm (or, more generally, the commitment to the idea that grounding ought to mirror metaphysical explanation), our metaphysics undergoes a beneficial enrichment. Grounding structures that

would be outlawed on normative grounds become legitimate theoretical options worthy of further attention. A very recent example of the fruitfulness of this approach is Cameron (2022), who explicitly defends non-wellfounded grounding structures (such as symmetric or coherentist structures of mutually grounded facts) by rejecting the connection between grounding and explanation. Interestingly, Cameron argues that a proper appreciation of the metaphysical tenability of these non-wellfounded views requires us a switch in our ‘theoretical perspective’ (2022, 108). The grounding perspectivalist would happily agree with this remark.

5.2 Structuralism about Grounding

I close by sketching a strategy to address the most pressing question that grounding perspectivalism faces. This view implies that what does the grounding depends on us in some crucial respects for our theorizing. For instance, the two cases I discussed suggest that the priority and asymmetry of grounding relationships are perspective-dependent matters. However, does the acceptance of grounding perspectivalism imply that there is no perspective-independent fact about the priority and directionality of grounding?

The considerations offered in this paper might prompt someone toward a positive answer. Accordingly, they might favour an account of metaphysical explanation that rejects the *Metaphysical Claim* in favour of a substantially deflated conception of grounding (e.g., Kovacs 2021, Taylor 2018, 2022; Thompson 2018, 2021; Miller and Norton 2017, 2022). But the answer to the previous question is negative.

The grounding perspectivalist framework does not rule out that there might be perspective-independent facts about the priority and asymmetry of grounding relationships. For example, a perspective-independent fact about the priority of determinates over determinables might obtain. Likewise,

perspective-independent symmetric grounding relationships could obtain. And if they do not, grounding is perspective-independently asymmetric.

The perspectivalist framework says that we cannot establish the priority and asymmetry of grounding by transcending our perspective. We are situated agents and inescapably so. Thus, the moral of grounding perspectivalism is a call for humility: we have no perspective-independent access to the grounding structure. But none the worse for that. The grounding perspectivalist could explore an intriguing argument to establish the existence of perspective-independent grounding facts.

Many sensible views appear to share the norm that grounding claims ought to be assessable across perspectives. The suggestion is to seek patterns of similarities and dissimilarities among various explanatorily successful perspectives adhering to this norm. Next, we identify the grounding relationships that are taken to obtain perspective-independently across a wide range of perspectives. (Presumably, these relationships should satisfy other requirements that render them fit to be considered; let us suppose that we achieve that.) After that, we run a familiar abductive argument to explain the patterns collected. If the fact that $[p]$ grounds $[q]$ obtains perspective-independently is the best explanation of why many perspectives accept that the perspective-independence of $[p]$ grounds $[q]$, then we have reasons to believe that $[p]$ grounds $[q]$ obtains perspective-independently.

The suggested approach may stumble on exciting cases. For example, it might not deliver a verdict on the priority or asymmetry of some grounding relationships involving specific facts. But cross-perspectival agreement may give us reason to believe that such facts stand in some grounding relationship. We may have strong cross-perspectival evidence for believing that $[p]$ and $[q]$ are related by grounding without being able to establish which is prior to what. If we employ the abductive strategy, we should conclude that there are grounding structures whose features, such as the places the relata occupy, are underdetermined. The resulting view licenses a form of structural realism

about grounding: we have more compelling abductive reasons to believe in the existence of grounding structures than in their features. This view is a welcome by-product of grounding perspectivalism. But this also is a good place to stop and postpone the discussion of this topic to another work.

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